

Acknowledgement

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Some Macrocyclic Complexes of Oxometal Ions. Part-I. Studies on some Oxozirconium(IV) Complexes

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In previous communications, we reported several transition metal complexes of different macrocyclic ligands¹⁻⁵. We now report the synthesis and characterisation of some oxozirconium(IV) complexes with two new 14-membered N₄-donor macro-

cycles, viz. dibenzo[e,f]-2,3,9,10-tetraphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene (L₁) and 1,4,8,11-tetradeca-2,3,9,10-dibenzocyclotetradeca-5,7,12,14-tetraene (L₂). All the complexes possess 1 : 1 stoichiometry, [ZrO(L)]X₂, where, L=L₁ or L₂; X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻, BF₄⁻ and 1/2 C₂O₄²⁻.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by initially refluxing the oxozirconium(IV) chloride (0.001 mol, 0.322 g) with *o*- or *m*-phenylenediamine (0.002 mol, 0.216 g) in methanol (50 ml) for 4 h. To it was then added benzil (0.002 mol, 0.420 g) for ligand L₁ and acetylacetone (0.002 mol, 0.200 ml) for ligand L₂ and further refluxed for 10–16 h. The resulting dark brown solution was purified by tlc and the complexes were crystallised from the light brown fraction using petroleum ether.

For preparing the complexes of other anions, oxozirconium(IV) chloride (0.001 mol, 0.322 g) was suspended in methanol (50 ml) and treated with silver perchlorate (nitrate/tetrafluoroborate) or ammonium thiocyanate (oxalate) (0.002 mol) and stirred for 4 h. The silver or ammonium chlorides so formed were filtered out and the resulting solution was treated as outlined above. The resulting dark brown complexes were filtered and dried. The complexes were characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, molecular weight, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis shows that in case of all the complexes only one mole of the tetradentate macrocycle, obtained by the template condensation

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Molar conductance* ^c Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
	Zr	O	H	N		
[ZrO(L ₁)](ClO ₄) ₂	10.88 (10.46)	— (55.17)	— (8.22)	— (8.64)	870 (868)	68.5 ^a
[ZrO(L ₁)](NO ₃) ₂	11.02 (11.45)	60.61 (60.88)	8.87 (8.52)	10.87 (10.57)	790 (795)	178 ^b
[ZrO(L ₁)](BF ₄) ₂	10.45 (10.79)	— (59.94)	— (8.82)	— (11.59)	828 (849)	178 ^b
[ZrO(L ₁)](Cl) ₂	12.90 (12.26)	64.88 (64.69)	8.87 (8.71)	7.86 (7.55)	788 (742)	169.1 ^b
[ZrO(L ₂)](SCN) ₂	11.08 (11.56)	69.52 (64.04)	8.78 (8.56)	10.48 (10.67)	789 (787)	167.4 ^b
[ZrO(L ₂)](C ₂ O ₄)	10.08 (10.74)	68.08 (63.84)	8.58 (8.81)	8.25 (6.61)	858 (847)	57.3 ^c
[ZrO(L ₂)](ClO ₄) ₂	14.55 (14.00)	— (40.62)	— (8.89)	— (8.62)	655 (650)	75.2 ^c
[ZrO(L ₂)](NO ₃) ₂	15.26 (15.88)	45.21 (45.91)	4.85 (4.17)	14.04 (14.61)	575 (576)	52.8 ^a
[ZrO(L ₂)](BF ₄) ₂	14.86 (14.61)	— (42.88)	— (8.85)	8.70 (8.99)	828 (828)	186 ^d
[ZrO(L ₂)](Cl) ₂	17.95 (17.48)	51.04 (50.58)	4.24 (4.59)	20.84 (20.78)	528 (522)	180 ^d
[ZrO(L ₂)](SCN) ₂	15.68 (16.05)	50.14 (50.74)	4.81 (4.28)	14.28 (14.82)	571 (567)	164.8 ^d
[ZrO(L ₂)](C ₂ O ₄)	14.25 (14.99)	47.87 (47.45)	8.65 (8.95)	9.83 (9.29)	614 (627)	178.8 ^d

*L₁ = C₂₀H₂₀N₄; L₂ = C₂₂H₂₂N₄. **In ^aEtOH, ^bMeOH, ^cDMSO, ^dacetone.

of two moles of *o*- or *m*-phenylenediamine and two mole of benzil or acetylacetone, is coordinated. The molar conductance measured in different solvents gives the required values for 1 : 2 electrolyte, thus suggesting that the anions are not coordinated as indicated in the formulae of the complexes.

In the ir spectra of the complexes, the NH₂ and CO stretching frequencies are absent and in their place a sharp band appears at 1 620 cm⁻¹ due to azomethine stretch and which suggests that Schiff base condensation with the consequent formation of macrocycle has occurred. The negative shift in its frequency by 20 cm⁻¹ or more is due to its coordination to zirconyl ion^{6,8}. This coordination is further supported by a sharp band at 430 ± 10 cm⁻¹ which has been assigned to (Zr←N) stretch⁶, and the Zr=O stretch is observed as a strong band at 970 ± 10 cm⁻¹ as found in other similar complexes⁷. The absorptions associated with anions in these complexes are identified at 1 085 and 620 cm⁻¹ for perchlorate⁹, 1 050 and 650 cm⁻¹ for tetrafluoroborate⁹, 1 360 and 810 cm⁻¹ for nitrate¹⁰, 1 640, 1 350, 890 and 770 cm⁻¹ for oxalate¹¹, 2 053, 745 and 484 cm⁻¹ for thiocyanate¹² and 570 cm⁻¹ for chloride¹³ and all these correspond to their uncoordinated nature.

In the ¹H nmr spectra of free ligands, multiplets are observed in the region δ 7.2–7.6 due to phenyl protons, while in ligand L₂ the CH₂ and CH₃ protons appear as singlet at δ 1.9 and 2.6, respectively. In the ¹H nmr spectra of the complex [ZrOL₁](ClO₄)₂, a single broad band appears at δ 7.4, while in the complex [ZrO(L₂)](ClO₄)₂, the CH₂ and CH₃ protons are seen at δ 2.1 and 2.9, respectively, and the multiplet corresponding to the phenyl protons appear at δ 7.6 and 7.8. This slight shift in the positions of these signals and the slight overlapping of the phenyl protons are due to the coordination from the adjacent nitrogen.

It is thus suggested that the ligands L₁ and L₂ completely encircle the oxo-ions through their four azomethine nitrogens and planar closed ring structures (1, 2) result. The oxygen atom of the ZrO moiety occupied the axial position projecting outside the planar macrocyclic plane. The coordination of anions will result in consequent ring opening with less stable structure and hence these are not coordinated.

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Rhenium(IV) Complexes with Pyrazole and Substituted-pyrazoles

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In this paper we report rhenium(IV) complexes of the type Re₂O₂Cl₂L₂, where L = pyrazole (Pz), 3-methylpyrazole (MePz), 3,5-dimethylpyrazole (DmPz), 3,4,5-trimethylpyrazole (TmPz) and 1,3,4,5-tetramethylpyrazole (TetmPz).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. 3-Methylpyrazole was obtained by decarboxylation of 3-methyl-5-carboxylic acid. While dimethylpyrazole was obtained by condensing acetyl acetone with hydrazine, tri- and tetra-methylpyrazoles were obtained by condensing 3-methyl acetyl acetone with hydrazine and methyl hydrazine respectively¹. The compounds were purified by fractional distillation. Potassium hexachlororhenate(IV) was prepared by the reduction of potassium